

Vocabulary for transdisciplinary research in affordable and sustainable housing

Deliverable 4.4

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 4.4. Vocabulary for transdisciplinary research
in affordable and sustainable housing

Version 1

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Executive summary

The **RE-DWELL vocabulary**, along with the **case library** (Deliverable 4.5) are essential tools for facilitating knowledge exchange among researchers within the RE-DWELL network. These resources aim to promote inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration in addressing the challenges of affordable and sustainable housing. Integrated on the RE-DWELL website (see Deliverables 5.2-5.7), they are publicly accessible, allowing a wide range of stakeholders to benefit from their content.

Researchers often approach complex issues like affordable and sustainable housing from their own disciplinary perspectives, which can lead to overlooking the specialized terminology, priorities, and methodologies of other fields. This lack of awareness can hinder collaboration and impede the construction of inter/transdisciplinary knowledge. The RE-DWELL vocabulary serves to bridge disciplinary boundaries among researchers—spanning architecture, urban planning, economics, social sciences, and sustainable management—helping them develop a comprehensive understanding of contemporary housing challenges.

The RE-DWELL vocabulary serves two main purposes:

1. **Summarizing research findings:** Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) distil their individual research findings into concepts that capture essential ideas related to affordable and sustainable housing.
2. **Sharing concepts:** The vocabulary facilitates the sharing of concepts among researchers, highlighting their relevance for the common research and encouraging cross-disciplinary communication.

As a repository of shared knowledge, the RE-DWELL vocabulary fosters a culture of collective learning among network members. Participants can access and engage with materials produced by their peers, broadening their understanding of various topics. It has been used as a learning resource in educational settings during network activities, such as peer reviewing, clustering concepts, and creating concept maps

The collaborative effort of constructing a shared vocabulary enhances individual research and fosters informed dialogue about critical issues that span different research areas. Moreover, it has enabled researchers to develop competencies in systems thinking, interpersonal communication, and knowledge co-creation within an interdisciplinary framework.

The vocabulary is implemented as an online tool developed by the ARC research group at La Salle School of Architecture. Its structure includes concept names and definitions, associated research areas, and links to related terms and cases. A total of 80 vocabulary entries (see Annex 1 - Concepts) have been created over the three-year project duration by ESRs, either individually or in collaboration with peers and supervisors.

In conclusion, the RE-DWELL vocabulary has proven to be an effective tool for developing essential research skills and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The content will remain available online, ensuring it continues to serve as a valuable resource for future learners addressing affordable and sustainable housing from a transdisciplinary perspective.

1. Introduction

The RE-DWELL [vocabulary](#) (Figure 1), together with the [case library](#) (Deliverable 4.5), serves as one of the key tools for facilitating knowledge exchange among researchers within the network. Both tools aim to foster interdisciplinarity by integrating the diverse perspectives and knowledge of researchers from various backgrounds, all focused on addressing the challenges of affordable and sustainable housing. These two tools are integrated on the RE-DWELL website, and their contents are available to the public (see Deliverables 5.2-5.5-5.6 and 5-7).

Figure 1. RE-DWELL on-line Vocabulary

In interdisciplinary research, where experts from different fields collaborate, creating a shared terminology is essential for effective communication and for gaining a comprehensive understanding of a multifaceted research area. The purpose of the RE-DWELL vocabulary is to foster the creation of a shared language. It serves as a common framework, ensuring that early-stage researchers (ESRs) from diverse backgrounds—such as architecture, urban planning, economics, social sciences, and sustainable management—can communicate effectively and understand each other's perspectives.

When researchers approach a complex issue like affordable and sustainable housing, they do so from the viewpoint of their own field of expertise. For instance, an architect may focus on the design and materials used in housing design and construction, while an economist might emphasise financial models or market dynamics. Each discipline not only has its own specialised terms, but also its own set of priorities, methods, and theoretical frameworks, which might be unknown to researchers from other backgrounds. This lack of awareness of the knowledge from other fields represents an creates barriers to collaboration.

To overcome this knowledge and linguistic gaps, creating a shared vocabulary becomes crucial. This vocabulary is not just about translating jargon but about building a mutual understanding of the key issues on affordable and sustainable housing procurement identified from multiple disciplinary viewpoints. By collaboratively identifying and defining core concepts from their respective fields, researchers can better understand each other's perspectives. This fosters more meaningful dialogue and allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the problem at hand.

To overcome knowledge and linguistic gaps, creating a shared vocabulary is essential to build mutual understanding of the key issues in affordable and sustainable housing procurement from multiple disciplinary viewpoints. By collaboratively identifying and defining core concepts within their respective fields, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of each other's perspectives. This fosters meaningful dialogue and enables a more comprehensive analysis of the problem.

2. Objectives and process

In the context of the transdisciplinary learning and research environment created in RE-DWELL (see Deliverable 4.6), the vocabulary developed by Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) served two key purposes:

- 1 **To summarize the main findings of individual research lines:** ESRs, while working on their PhD thesis, engaged in focused research within a specific direction. The vocabulary allowed them to distil their findings into concise concepts, capturing the essential ideas and results of their work. These concepts served as summaries of the critical insights gained in their respective research areas, expressed in a language that could be easily understood by fellow researchers.
- 2 **To share concepts with peers, highlighting their relevance to the shared research issue:** Communication across disciplines requires making implicit knowledge and assumptions explicit. This involves not only describing a concept, but also explaining its relevance in the context of affordable and sustainable housing and the connections to other areas of research.

3. Implementation

The vocabulary was implemented as an online tool integrated into the [project website](#). It was designed and developed by the ARC research group from the coordinating team of the School

of Architecture La Salle, which had already experience with developing online vocabularies for housing studies carried out in previous EU projects¹.

The vocabulary structure is as follows (Figure 2):

- **Concept:** The unique name assigned to each term.
- **Definitions:** Multiple descriptions of a term, each associated with one of the three RE-DWELL research areas.

Figure 2. Structure of the vocabulary: concepts, definitions and research areas

The description of a vocabulary entry includes the following fields:

- Description
- Reference sources
- Research area

¹ Madrazo, L., & Massey, J. (2005). HOUSING@ 21. EU. A web-based pedagogic platform for the study of housing in Europe. In *Proceedings of the 23rd eCAADe Conference*. 23rd eCAADe Conference, Lisbon, 21-25 of September 2005.

- Related concepts
- Related cases
- Additional information (files, images, videos)

The entries in the vocabulary can be either single-authored or collaboratively written by network members, including ESRs, supervisors, and partner organizations. They are managed in the back office of the website (Figure 3). Guidelines and recommendations to describe the terms were provided to researchers (see Annex 2 - Guidelines).

The figure consists of two side-by-side screenshots of the RE-DWELL website's back office interface for managing the vocabulary.

The left screenshot shows a list of vocabulary entries. The table has the following columns: ID, name, Date Created, and Definitions. The entries include terms like Homelessness, Financial Viability, Green Land Value Tax, Grant-of-use cooperative housing, Energy Communities, Homeless, Techno-optimism, Housing Quality, Financial Wellbeing, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Circular Economy, Thermal Insulation and Airtightness, Prebound Effect, Ecosocial Policy, Social Infrastructure, social infrastructure, Product Platform, Flexibility, Third place, Deliberative Democracy, Environmentally Sustainable Social Housing, Framework, Urban Informality, Direct Action, Collaborative housing, Social Innovation, New Municipalism, Precariat, Financialization, Collaborative Planning, Design Activism, Spatial Agency, Capability Approach, Targeted Universalism, Housing Allowance, Trauma Informed Design, and Third place.

The right screenshot shows the 'New Definition' form. It includes a 'Definition' text area, a 'References' text area, an 'Area' dropdown menu (set to 'Design, planning and building'), an 'Owners' dropdown menu (set to 'Manuel, Leonora - supervisor'), and several empty text areas for 'Vocabulary Related', 'Case Related', and 'Publications Related'. There are also checkboxes for 'Published', 'Images', 'Files', and 'Videos', each with an 'Add' button. At the bottom right, there are 'Cancel' and 'Save' buttons.

Figure 3. RE-DWELL website back office: Vocabulary

The information entered in the back-office is displayed on the public website (Figure 4). Additionally, it includes a relational map that visually represents the connections between the reference term and other concepts, cases, publications, and blog posts (Figure 5). This map allows users to navigate the website's content in an associative manner, exploring the interconnections between various elements.

RE-DWELL About Training [Energy poverty](#) Resources Buy Items Contact

Home > Knowledge base > Vocabulary > Energy Poverty Definition

[Back to Vocabulary](#)

Energy Poverty

 T. Cloon [ESRH](#)

Area Policy and financing

The in-depth study of energy poverty as a social phenomenon commenced in the late 19th century through the works of British social researchers Booth and Rowntree (O'Connor, 2018). This area was characterized by significant social and economic transformation, and these scholars were troubled by the living conditions and welfare of impoverished urban populations, who were residing in congested and unsanitary environments.

Throughout the 20th century, poverty in policy contexts became quite narrowly defined as a lack of income. However, it was another social concern in the UK that led to the development of concepts like fuel poverty or 'energy poverty' a century after Booth and Rowntree (1). Following the 1973 oil crisis, the Child Poverty Action Group took the initiative to address how increasing energy costs were affecting low-income households in the UK (Johnson & Rowland, 1978). As essentials like heating, electricity, and fuel became necessary for maintaining a decent standard of living in modern British society, this advocacy group pushed for government financial support. Later, Bradburn and Mutton (1983) introduced a narrower definition of energy poverty: 'the inability to afford adequate heat in the home'. Since then, studies on energy poverty have typically excluded motor fuel, as this falls under transport poverty, a related but separate area of study (Maitelli et al., 2017).

Energy poverty, as defined by Bouzarovski and Petrova (2015, p. 33), refers to 'the inability to secure or afford sufficient domestic energy services that allow for participation in society'. Although the precise boundaries of relevant domestic energy usage are still debated, this definition expands beyond mere heating as it encompasses energy used for cooling, which is particularly relevant in warmer climates (Thomson et al., 2019). Moreover, it enables a socially and culturally dependent understanding of what it means to participate in society (Middlemiss et al., 2019). On 15 September 2023, the European Union (2023) officially defined energy poverty as 'a household's lack of access to essential energy services, where such services provide basic levels and decent standards of living and health, including adequate heating, hot water, cooling, lighting, and energy to power appliances, in the relevant national context, existing national social policy and other relevant national policies, created by a combination of factors, including at least non-affordability, insufficient disposable income, high energy expenditure and poor energy efficiency of homes'.

The doctoral thesis and subsequent book by Rosalee Bradburn, 'Fuel significant breakthrough in energy poverty research. She emphasized the detrimental impact of inefficient housing on health and quality of life. In the decade that followed, substantial literature confirmed her qualitative findings (Thomson et al., 2017). Notably, studies have demonstrated the adverse effects of living in energy poverty on physical health (Liddell & Morris, 2010), mental health (Liddell & Quinley, 2015), stress levels (Loughlin & Hargrave, 2018), social isolation (Harrison et al., 2005), and absenteeism (Howden-Chapman et al., 2007).

Boardman's work introduced an indicator that has remained influential to this date, although it was not the first attempt to operationalise the concept of fuel poverty (Hetherwood & Hancock, 1979). His '2M' indicator categorises a household an energy poor if it needs to allocate twice the median share of its budget for energy expenses to heat its home adequately. Boardman calculated this threshold to be 30% at that time. Due to its simplicity and ease of comprehension, many governments directly adopted this 30% threshold without considering specific contextual circumstances. Since the early 1980s, numerous attempts have been made to develop alternative indicators. Highly influential ones include Low Income High Cost (LIHC) by John Hills (2012), Low Income Low Energy Efficiency (LILEE) that subsequently became the official British indicator (BEIS, 2022), and a 'hidden' energy poverty indicator by Meyer et al., (2018). Critics of these indicators focus, amongst other things, on their simplicity and perceived 'technocratic' approach (Cloon et al., 2023; Middlemiss, 2017).

This marked the beginning of significant government commitment, initially in the UK and later in other countries to address energy poverty. Although certain forms of cold weather payments had already been introduced by the UK's Conservative administrations, it was under the successive governments of Blair and Brown, following the publication of Boardman's work, that programmes such as the Winter Fuel Payment and Warm Home Discount were implemented (Boh et al., 2012). The UK examples highlight bipartisan support for addressing energy poverty, with both the Conservatives and Labour backing these efforts. This policy objective has also gained momentum in various legislative contexts, leading the EU to incorporate energy poverty alleviation as a fundamental pillar of the European Green Deal and a specific goal of its landmark Social Climate Fund (European Commission, 2021).

Over the last three decades, public interest in energy poverty as a 'wicked' problem has surged, particularly during the recent energy crisis. This crisis began in 2021 when energy markets tightened due to a post-pandemic economic rebound, and it worsened dramatically after Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 (IEA, 2023). Extensive research on the impact of this price surge on energy poverty levels has been carried out throughout Europe and globally (Guan et al., 2023; Spiesberger, 2023). Consequently, energy poverty has become a significant focal point in discussions related to the 'just transition', especially within the realm of energy justice, as it serves as a valuable concept for targeting policies towards a specific vulnerable group in this context (Carnoso & De Vido, 2023).

(1) Fuel poverty' and 'energy poverty' are used interchangeably, with the former being more common in the UK and the latter in mainland Europe (Bouzarovski & Petrova, 2015). Previously, scholars in the UK used 'energy poverty' to denote a lack of access to energy and 'fuel poverty' when affordability was the concern (Li et al., 2018). However, this distinction is no longer maintained.

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Created on 17-10-2023 | Updated on 06-10-2023

Related definitions

Just Transition
Author: T. Cloon [ESRH](#)

Justice theory is as old as philosophical thought itself, but the contemporary debate often departs from the Rawlsian understanding of justice (Velezquez, Andre, Daniels, & Meyer, 1990). Rawls (1971) argued that societal harmony depends on the extent to which community members believe their political institutions treat them justly. His First...

Created on 01-09-2022 | Updated on 09-09-2022

Performance Gap in Retrofit
Author: S. Farman [ESRH](#)

The performance gap in retrofit refers to the disparity between the predicted and actual energy consumption after a retrofit project, measured in kWh/m2/year. This discrepancy can be substantial, occasionally reaching up to five times the predicted energy usage (Tranovic, 2018). Sunjka-Blanc & Galvin (2012) identify four key factors as contributing to...

Created on 08-09-2023 | Updated on 01-10-2023

Social Value
Author: L. Reardon [ESRH](#)

Social value (SV) is a wide-ranging concept that encompasses the wider economic, social and environmental well-being impacts of a specific activity. Given its applicability across various sectors, diverse interpretations and definitions exist, often leading to its interchangeable use with other terms, such as social impact. This interchangeability may...

Created on 09-10-2023 | Updated on 02-12-2023

Financial Wellbeing
Author: K. Knight [ESRH](#)

Financial wellbeing is an emerging concept with various definitions, many of which focus on the financial capabilities of individuals. A household's financial wellbeing encompasses its capacity to comfortably meet current and ongoing financial responsibilities, fostering a sense of security about future obligations while enjoying the ability to make life choices (Aubrey ...)

Created on 16-10-2024 | Updated on 04-10-2024

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Figure 4. Vocabulary entry “Energy poverty” displayed on the website

Figure 5. Visual map with a focus on the concept “Energy Poverty” displaying the links between researchers and research outputs

In addition to the entry published on the website, researchers were invited to share the references used in a Mendeley account (Figure 6) created for the RE-DWELL project.

AUTHORS	YEAR	TITLE	SOURCE	ADDED	FILE
Hardt, Michael; Negri, Antonio	2009	Commonwealth		18/10/2022	
Harvey, David	2008	The right to the city	New Left Review	18/10/2022	
Ialoue, Christian	2015	Governing the Urban Commons		18/10/2022	
Ialoue, Christian; De Nicolis, Elena; Suma...	2019	The Internet of Humans (IoH) Human Rights and Co-Governance to Achieve Tech Justice in the City	Law and Ethics of Human Rights	18/10/2022	
Lefebvre, Henri	1996	The Right to the City	Writings on Cities	18/10/2022	
Lohmann, Roger A	2016	The Ostroms' Commons Revisited	Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector ...	18/10/2022	
McLaren, Duncan; Aggeman, Julian	2015	Sharing Cities: A Case for Truly Smart and Sustainable Cities		18/10/2022	
Ostrom, Elinor	1990	Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action		18/10/2022	
Parr, Adrian	2015	Urban Debt, Neoliberalism and the Politics of the Commons	Theory, Culture & Society	18/10/2022	
Shareable	2018	Sharing Cities: Activating the Urban Commons		18/10/2022	
Linebaugh, Peter	2008	The Magna Carta Manifesto: Liberties and Commons for All		18/10/2022	
Hess, Charlotte	2008	Mapping the New Commons	SSRN Electronic Journal	18/10/2022	
Stavrides, Stavros	2015	Common Space as Threshold Space: Urban Commoning in Struggles to Re-appropriate Public Space	FOOTPRINT	18/10/2022	
Stavrides, Stavros	2016	Common Space: The City as Commons		18/10/2022	
Hardin, Garrett	1968	The Tragedy of the Commons	Science, New Series	18/10/2022	
Deltenbaugh-Losse, Mary; Zimmermann, ...	2015	The Urban Commons Cookbook: Strategies and Insights for Creating and Maintaining Urban Commons		18/10/2022	
Borch, Christian; Kornberger, Martin	2015	Urban commons - rethinking the city		18/10/2022	
Angelis, Massimo De; Stavrides, Stavros	2009	Beyond Markets or States: Commoning as Collective PracticePublic Interview with Massimo De Angelis and Stavros ...	An Architektur	18/10/2022	
Zahiri, Sahar; Elisharkawy, Heba	2018	Towards energy-efficient retrofit of council housing in London: Assessing the impact of occupancy and energy-use pat...	Energy and Buildings	6/7/2022	
Tabata, Tomohiro; Tsai, Pei	2020	Fuel poverty in Summer: An empirical analysis using microdata for Japan	Science of the Total Environment	6/7/2022	

Figure 6. References used in the vocabulary entries shared in the Mendeley group

The vocabulary and case library content has been exported as an RDF dataset, including metadata that third parties can use in applications related to housing affordability and sustainability at various scales. This dataset is publicly available on [Zenodo](#).

4. Vocabulary entries

Over the three-year project duration, a total of 80 vocabulary entries have been created ESRs, either individually or in collaboration with peers and supervisors. Each term is linked to a specific research area, distributed as follows:

- **Design, Planning, and Building:** 40 entries
- **Community Participation:** 21 entries
- **Policy and Financing:** 19 entries

This distribution reflects the predominant backgrounds of the ESRs, who primarily come from architecture and planning disciplines. Most entries were authored individually by ESRs, with 8 entries produced collaboratively among peers and 14 developed in partnership with supervisors.

Even though the vocabulary structured allowed for multiple definitions of the same term, provided by multiple authors, this feature was only used in three key terms: affordability (3 definitions), sustainability (5) and transdisciplinarity (3).

In addition to entries related to research areas, there have been entries focusing on research methodology such as “Capability Approach”, “Critical Utopian Action Research”, “Framework”, “Direct Action”, “Path Dependence.”

5. Vocabulary as learning tool and resource

During the network activities, we used the content collectively created in the vocabulary as a learning tool and resource in various contexts while adopting a diverse range of learning strategies to foster the collaborative creation of knowledge across fields and researchers.

- **RMT1 course: vocabulary workshop – October 2021.** A session of this [course](#) introduced students to have a knowledge of key housing terminology. The task for students was to propose the terms and critically reflect on their importance for their own research and for the overall field of affordable and sustainable housing. The collective work was summarized in a table, with the proposed concepts aligned to the researchers/institutions (Figure 7).

Resource for RMT1_Task 1
LIST OF KEY TERMS SUGGESTED BY RE-DWELL RESEARCHERS

Key term	RE-DWELL institution(s) that proposed the term
housing affordability	UREAD CSS UPV UNIZG FUNITEC TUD
housing action-research collaboration	ISCTE
housing actors	UGA
housing advocacy	UNIZG
housing co-creation	UCY
housing co-design	UCY
housing co-housing	CSS UNIZG
housing co-production of housing	UNIZG
housing co-production of knowledge	ISCTE
housing collaborative design process	UCY USFD
housing collaborative housing research	UCY USFD
sustainable communities	FUNITEC USFD
housing cooperatives / cooperation	CSS UPV
urban affordability crisis	TUD
urban affordability decision support method	UPV
housing delivery	UREAD
housing eco villages	FUNITEC
housing energy poverty	TUD
housing energy poverty	CSS
housing finance	TUD
housing frame innovation	ISCTE
housing, urban governance	UGA UNIZG TUD
housing, urban green housing	FUNITEC
urban health / healthy housing	CSS FUNITEC UREAD
housing home	TUD
housing human-centered (design)	UPV
housing inclusive (housing)	TUD
housing industrialised (housing)	FUNITEC
housing innovations	UNIZG
housing integrated knowledge production	ISCTE
housing knowledge-in-practice	ISCTE
housing landlord (and equivalents in other languages)	UREAD
housing learning by doing	ISCTE
Social Life Cycle Assessment (LCA- SLCA)	CSS
housing liveability	FUNITEC
housing market rental	CSS
housing mass-customized housing	FUNITEC
housing mixed methods	UGA
housing mortgage	CSS
housing multicriteria assessment	UPV
housing multidimensionality	USFD
housing negotiation	UGA
housing neighbourhood	CSS
housing objectivity / subjectivity	UGA
housing participation	UREAD
housing place	UREAD
public policies	UGA UPV TUD
public post-occupancy evaluation	FUNITEC
housing practice-based research	ISCTE
housing quality	TUD
housing quality of life	UGA UREAD
housing reflective practice	ISCTE
housing regeneration schemes	UGA
housing regime	CSS
housing research by design	ISCTE
urban resilience	UGA FUNITEC TUD
housing retrofit / renovation	UREAD UPV
inter-, cross-, trans- sectoral	USFD
inter-, cross-, trans- social (rental) housing	CSS UNIZG FUNITEC USFD
inter-, cross-, trans- social evaluation	UGA
housing as social investment	UNIZG
housing as social mix	UNIZG
housing stakeholders	UGA
housing state funded housing	UREAD
housing subsidies	CSS
housing sustainability	UREAD UNIZG FUNITEC TUD UPV
housing tenure	CSS UREAD
housing transdisciplinary research	ISCTE
housing transitions	UGA
housing urban development	TUD
social / urban vulnerability	FUNITEC UGA
social / urban welfare regime	CSS
social / urban well-being	UGA UPV FUNITEC

Figure 7. Concepts proposed by researchers produced in the RMT1 course

The responses provided by researchers to the course evaluation form confirmed the usefulness of the vocabulary tool:

“The session 5 on vocabulary was very useful for me, as it related to research methods.”

“The best part of the whole course! It was interesting and useful to understand the importance of identifying my research key terms from the start. Besides, it simplified the idea of definitions.”

“Most relevant as we are at the stage of dealing with definitions and fit well with ESRs timing.”

“The vocabulary tasks have been extremely useful and related to my individual work. It has also helped to forged new connections with ESRs which have led to other fruitful conversations about our projects and the potential to write a joint paper.”

- Budapest workshop – March 2022

A session dedicated to working on the vocabulary was included in the [workshop programme](#). It consisted of two parts.

1. Peer review of entries. ESRs were tasked with peer-reviewing a vocabulary entry written by another peer (Figures 8 and 9), answering the following questions:

- Is it relevant to the network's research?
- Is it intelligible and well-written?
- Are the references used correctly? Do they provide authoritative arguments that are well integrated into the narrative?
- Do the references conform to APA style?

2. Hands-on team activity. The ESRs, organized into teams, worked with the content produced so far in the vocabulary (Figure 10):

- Relating terms
- Creating groups of terms

The image shows a slide titled "Specific comments" with three bullet points. To the right, there are three text boxes containing excerpts from a document being reviewed, with specific words highlighted in yellow and pink. The slide footer includes the RE-DWELL logo, the text "Budapest Workshop | Peer Review", and the number "4".

Specific comments

- Better to reference peer reviewed sources for the base definition rather than conference proceedings (Smith, 2007).
- Clarify the design stages, from the briefing stage until deconstruction for instance - is an LCCA cradle-to-cradle? What about profiting from waste materials? Or in relation to energy efficiency; energy-positive buildings can supply back to the grid (and provide income).
- Would start this sentence with "However,..." as this sentence contradicts the previous statement - also preferable not to start the sentence with "Moreover" twice in close succession.

The life cycle costs (LCC) of owning or renting a house incorporate initial capital acquisition costs, financing costs, operational costs, and finally its disposable costs when applicable (Goh & Sun, 2016; Kubba, 2010; Smith, 2007). LCC is the sum of all these costs that are reduced to the present-day values

Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) is commonly adopted in the building industry by cost estimating engineers to assist investment decision making (Liu & Qian, 2019). It is used as an economic analysis method to estimate the costs of different design alternatives over its whole life cycle from early design stages where the most influential building decisions are made. For instance, research has shown that

designing and constructing the building. Moreover, 80% of the operation, maintenance, and replacement costs can be influenced in the first 20% of the design process (Karatas & El-Rayes, 2014). Thus, LCCA would have a substantial influence when performed early in the design process to allow any needed design refinements or modifications to take place (Kubba, 2010). Moreover, prioritizing the reduction of initial costs when selecting a design alternative, regardless their effect on maintenance and repair costs, may not lead to an economically efficient building during its life cycle (Rad et al., 2021).

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Figure 8. Peer review of the term "Life Cycle Cost Analysis" by Aya Elghandour, conducted by Annette Davis

Specific Suggestions

- Start with the definition: **sustainability is...**
- Try to be consistent on the way you quote (*italics* or *regular*)
- Quotations here don't offer much. Paragraph 3 in your own words might have a better flow and more direct understanding. It is slightly 'wordy'.

1 • Sustainability has been a **focal point of interest** for the past 20 years for researchers, policy makers, corporations as well as local communities, and activist groups, among others (Purvis et al., 2015). A relatively general and ambiguous term, sustainability is primarily defined as **"meeting the needs and desires of present generations without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs"** (United Nations, 1987) and is often interpreted as the strategies adopted towards sustainability with the latter being the overall goal/vision (Desenford, 2000).

2 • The ambiguity and vagueness that characterises both of these terms has contributed to their leap into the global mainstream as well as the broad political consensus regarding their value and significance (Mebratu, 1998; Purvis et al., 2015), rendering them one of the dominant discourses in environmental, socio-political and economic issues (Tulloch, 2013). It is, however, highly contested whether their institutionalisation is a positive development. Tulloch, and Tulloch & Nielson (2013; 2014) argue that these terms - as they are currently understood - are the outcome of the **"colonisation of environmental thought and action"** which, **during the 1960s and 1970s**, argued that economic growth and ecological sustainability within the capitalist system were contradictory pursuits. This "colonisation" resulted in the disempowerment of such discourses and their subsequent **"subordination to neoliberal hegemony"** (Tulloch & Neilson, 2014, p. 26). Thus, sustainability and sustainable development, when articulated within neoliberalism, not only reinforce it, through practices such as greenwashing, but also fail to address the intrinsic issues of a system that operates on, safeguards, and prioritises economic profit over social and ecological well-being (Jakobsen, 2022).

3 • Murray Bookchin, in *"The Ecology of Freedom"* proposes that social and environmental issues are profoundly entangled, and their origin can be traced to **"the very notion of the domination of nature by man [which] stems from the very real domination of human by human"** (1982). In order to re-radicalise sustainability, we need to undertake the utopian task of revisiting our intra-relating, breaking-down the underlying hierarchical relations, and re-stitching our social fabric. As Nabeel Hamdi suggested, (2004, p. xix) **"in order to do something big [...] one starts with something small and one starts where it counts"**. The intra-relating between and within the different molecules a society consists of, i.e. the communities, is what defines how sustainability is understood and practised (or performed) within both these different communities and the society they form. In other words, a reconfigured, non-hierarchical, non-dominating intra-relate is what can allow for an equitable, **long-term setting for human activity and interaction** (Dempsey et al., 2011, p. 290), i.e. a sustainable community/society.

Figure 9. Peer review of the term “Sustainability through community participation” by Effrosyni Roussou, conducted by Androniki Pappa

Figure 10. Clustering and interrelating concepts from the vocabulary, by Effrosyni Roussou

The responses provided by researchers to the vocabulary session in the workshop evaluation were the following:

“It was really good and more useful to discuss in small groups”

“I really like the way in which the session was addressed. Instead of giving another presentation of a peer review, we had the chance to discuss with our colleagues and give and get more insights about our writing in a more informal but informative fashion.”

“(...) I genuinely appreciate shifting the work to groups, and it was helpful and more efficient.”

6. Competencies

The collaborative construction of a shared vocabulary enables researchers to develop competencies in systems thinking, interpersonal skills, and knowledge co-creation within an interdisciplinary context.

The process of developing a shared vocabulary fosters collaboration and the integration of diverse perspectives. By collectively defining terms and concepts, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the interconnections and relationships within the various fields involved in affordable and sustainable housing. Establishing a common language helps bridge gaps between disciplines, enabling researchers to leverage their unique strengths and insights. Integrating this vocabulary tool into training activities not only facilitates knowledge acquisition but also promotes critical thinking and fosters meaningful discussions among researchers from different fields.

7. Conclusions

The vocabulary served as a repository of shared knowledge, providing researchers with access to their peers' research, summarized in key concepts. The glossary fostered an environment of collective learning, enabling participants to learn from each other's research findings, methodologies, and perspectives. By engaging with the vocabulary, network members expanded their understanding of various topics related to affordable and sustainable housing, reaching beyond their areas of expertise.

The vocabulary will remain publicly accessible beyond the project's lifetime and has the potential to grow further, with additional contributions from former ESRs and other interested parties who are granted access. This will allow it to continue serving as a valuable resource for future researchers, helping them frame issues related to affordable and sustainable housing from a transdisciplinary perspective. Moreover, the current vocabulary can be used by third parties as a learning resource in educational activities, particularly at the graduate and postgraduate levels.

Annex 1 - Concepts

Table 1 summarizes the terms included in the vocabulary, with links to the corresponding website content for further details.

Table 1. Vocabulary entries

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
Affordability (8)	Policy and financing	Affordability (30) Affordability (41) Social Housing Measuring Housing Affordability Housing Allowance Financialization Deliberative Democracy Financial Wellbeing Housing Quality Techno-optimism Homelessness Thermal Insulation & Airtightness		Christophe Verrier (ESR3)
Affordability (30)	Design, planning and building	Affordability (8) Financial Wellbeing	Diagoon Houses Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands Knight's Walk (Lambeth's Homes)	Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		Housing Regime Mass Customisation Life Cycle Costing Measuring Housing Affordability	La Borda The Elwood Project, Vancouver, Washington	
Affordability (41)	Policy and financing	Affordability (8) Housing Regime Housing Affordability Financial Wellbeing Green Land Value Tax Viability		Marietta Haffner (supervisor) Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)
Asset-based Welfare	Policy and financing			Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
BIM	Design, planning and building	Transdisciplinarity Mass Customisation Life Cycle Costing	Solar Decathlon Europe 2022	Annette Davis (ESR 1) Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)
Building Decarbonisation	Design, planning and building	Sustainability Sustainability Built Environment	85 Social Housing Units in Cornellà Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework Deben Fields (Garrison Lane) ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation Knight's Walk (Lambeth's Homes) North Wingfield Road social housing complex.	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Capability Approach	Community participation	Community Empowerment		Zoe Tzika (ESR 10)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
Circular Economy	Design, planning and building	Design for Disassembly Industrialised Construction Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	Annette Davis (ESR 1)
Co-creation	Community participation	Social Value	DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Diagoon Houses Die Baupiloten Berlin La Borda Marmalade Lane Navarinou Park Patch22	Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8) Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9)
Collaborative Governance	Community participation	Housing Governance Community Empowerment	Fondazione per l'Innovazione Urbana (FIU) Lleialtat Santseca Civic Centre Self-Organisation in a New Dutch Suburb: Housing development in Oosterwold	Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)
Collaborative housing	Policy and financing	Participatory Approaches		Lucia Chaloin (ESR 3)
Collaborative Planning	Design, planning and building	Co-creation Collaborative Governance Placemaking	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework	Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)
Community Empowerment	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Social Sustainability	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework Co-operative housing project in Croatia: the case of the city of Križevci DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Diagoon Houses La Borda LiLa4Green Marmalade Lane Mehr als wohnen – More than housing Navarinou Park Rural Studio The Elwood Project, Vancouver, Washington	Zoe Tzika (ESR 10)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
Community-led Housing	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Urban Commons	Can70 senior cooperative housing: Aging in community Co-operative housing project in Croatia: the case of the city of Križevci La Borda Mehr als wohnen – More than housing	Zoe Tzika (ESR 10)
Critical Utopian Action Research	Community participation			Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Deliberative Democracy	Community participation	Affordability Co-creation Housing Governance Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Just Transition Urban Commons Community-led Housing Post-occupancy Evaluation Public-civic Partnership		Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15) Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Design Activism	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Urban Commons	Die Baupiloten Berlin	Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9)
Design for Dissassembly	Design, planning and building		85 Social Housing Units in Cornellà APROP Temporary social housing for people at risk to residential exclusion Flexwoningen Oosterdreef Patch22	Annette Davis (ESR 1)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
			Solar Decathlon Europe 2022 WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	
Direct Action	Community participation	Urban Commons Spatial Agency Design Activism	Navarinou Park	Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9)
Ecosocial Policy	Policy and financing	Just Transition		Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Energy Communities	Design, planning and building			Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Energy Poverty	Policy and financing	Just Transition	A Combined Energy Efficiency and Levelling Up Scheme: the Dutch 'Volkshuisvestingsfonds' Pre-1919 Niddrie Road Retrofit – An Example of Care for Climate and Health	Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Energy Retrofit	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Sustainability	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework HOUSEFUL: Els Mestres, Sabadell Pre-1919 Niddrie Road Retrofit – An Example of Care for Climate and Health The Sutton Estate Regeneration, Chelsea	Saskia Furman (ESR 2)
Environmentally Sustainable Social Housing	Design, planning and building	Social Sustainability Sustainability Sustainability Built Environment Mass Customisation Social Housing Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Deben Fields (Garrison Lane) Knight's Walk (Lambeth's Homes)	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Financial Wellbeing	Design, planning and building	Affordability Community Empowerment Just Transition Social Sustainability Urban Commons Life Cycle Costing Housing	A Combined Energy Efficiency and Levelling Up Scheme: the Dutch 'Volkshuisvestingsfonds' Can70 senior cooperative housing: Aging in community ESG for Social Housing Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands La Borda Pre-1919 Niddrie Road Retrofit – An Example of Care for Climate and Health	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		Affordability Energy Poverty Social Value Financialization	York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	
Financialization	Policy and financing	Affordability Asset-based Welfare		Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
Flexibility	Design, planning and building	Community Empowerment Design for Dissassembly Industrialised Construction Open Building	Diagoon Houses Flexwoningen Oosterdreef La Borda Marmalade Lane Patch22	Carolina Martín (ESR 14)
Framework	Design, planning and building	Co-creation Housing Retrofit Participatory Approaches Housing Regime Sustainability Sustainability Built Environment Housing Policy	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Grant-of-use cooperative housing	Design, planning and building		Can70 senior cooperative housing: Aging in community La Borda	Zoe Tzika (ESR 10)
Green Land Value Tax	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Affordability	Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands	Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)
Homelessness	Policy and financing	Affordability Just Transition		Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
Housing Affordability	Design, planning and building	Sustainability Life Cycle Costing Affordability Social Housing	ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation LILAC_Low Impact Living Affordable Community_Leeds Mason Place Apartments Rural Studio The Social Climate Fund: Materialising Just Transition Principles? WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		Community-led Housing	York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	
Housing Allowance	Design, planning and building	Affordability Housing Policy		Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
Housing Governance	Policy and financing		ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation Housing Fund of the Republic of Slovenia	Marko Horvat (ESR 6) Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Housing Policy	Policy and financing		ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands	Marietta Haffner (supervisor) Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)
Housing Quality	Design, planning and building	Affordability Energy Retrofit Community Empowerment Asset-based Welfare Social Sustainability Sustainability Built Environment Housing Affordability Measuring Housing Affordability Post-occupancy Evaluation Design Activism		Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)
Housing Regime	Policy and financing	Housing Governance	ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation	Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Housing Retrofit	Design, planning and building		Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework HOUSEFUL: Els Mestres, Sabadell Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands Pre-1919 Niddrie Road Retrofit – An Example of Care for Climate and	Saskia Furman (ESR 2) Zoe Tzika (ESR 10) Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
			Health The Sutton Estate Regeneration, Chelsea	
Indoor Thermal Comfort	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Participatory Approaches Energy Retrofit Just Transition Social Sustainability Sustainability Social Housing	Knight's Walk (Lambeth's Homes)	Saskia Furman (ESR 2)
Industrialised Construction	Design, planning and building	BIM Mass Customisation Design for Disassembly	85 Social Housing Units in Cornellà APROP Temporary social housing for people at risk to residential exclusion Diagoon Houses Flexwoningen Oosterdreef Patch22 Solar Decathlon Europe 2022 WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	Annette Davis (ESR 1) Carolina Martín (ESR 14)
Just Transition	Policy and financing	Housing Governance	A Combined Energy Efficiency and Levelling Up Scheme: the Dutch 'Volkshuisvestingsfonds' ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation Targeting and Policy Efficiency: Exploring the Intended Reform of the Warm Home Discount The Social Climate Fund: Materialising Just Transition Principles?	Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Design, planning and building	BIM Life Cycle Costing Design for Disassembly Industrialised Construction	WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	Annette Davis (ESR 1)
Life Cycle Costing	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Energy Retrofit Community Empowerment Affordability Sustainability	Dalarnas Villa - Built Research Project Investigating Sustainability WikiHouse: South Yorkshire Housing Association	Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		Sustainability Built Environment Transdisciplinarity Mass Customisation		
Mass Customisation	Design, planning and building	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Affordability Transdisciplinarity		Carolina Martín (ESR 14)
Measuring Housing Affordability	Design, planning and building	Affordability Sustainability Life Cycle Costing Housing Affordability	ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Aya Elghandour (ESR 4)
New Municipalism	Design, planning and building			Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)
Open Building	Design, planning and building	Participatory Approaches Sustainability Built Environment Mass Customisation Design for Dissassembly Industrialised Construction	Patch22	Carolina Martín (ESR 14)
Participatory Approaches	Community participation	Co-creation	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Die Baupiloten Berlin La Borda LiLa4Green Marmalade Lane Navarinou Park York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5) Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15) Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
Path Dependence	Policy and financing	Housing Governance Housing Regime Housing Policy		Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
Performance Gap in Retrofit	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Energy Retrofit Housing Policy Energy Poverty Building Decarbonisation		Saskia Furman (ESR 2)
Placemaking	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Urban Commons	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework Die Baupiloten Berlin LiLa4Green Navarinou Park	Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)
Post-occupancy Evaluation	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Performance Gap in Retrofit	Deben Fields (Garrison Lane)	Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15)
Prebound Effect	Design, planning and building	Housing Retrofit Energy Retrofit Performance Gap in Retrofit		Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Precariat	Policy and financing	Social Sustainability Housing Affordability		Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Product Platform	Design, planning and building	Mass Customisation Housing Affordability Design for Disassembly		Carolina Martín (ESR 14)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		Industrialised Construction		
Public-civic Partnership	Community participation	Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Urban Commons Placemaking		Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)
Social Housing	Policy and financing	Affordability Housing Retrofit Housing Governance Housing Regime Asset-based Welfare	85 Social Housing Units in Cornellà Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation HOUSEFUL: Els Mestres, Sabadell LILAC_Low Impact Living Affordable Community_Leeds Mason Place Apartments North Wingfield Road social housing complex.	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Social Infrastructure	Community participation	Co-creation Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Urban Commons Collaborative Governance Placemaking Spatial Agency		Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)
Social Innovation	Policy and financing			Adriana Diaconu (supervisor) Lucia Chaloin (ESR 3)
Social Sustainability	Community participation	Housing Governance Collaborative Governance	DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Diagoon Houses Flexwoningen Oosterdreef La Borda LiLa4Green Lleialtat Santsenca Civic Centre Mason Place Apartments Navarinou Park Rural Studio	Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
			The Elwood Project, Vancouver, Washington York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	
Social Value	Community participation	Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Energy Poverty Post-occupancy Evaluation Placemaking	Broadwater Farm Urban Design Framework Co-operative housing project in Croatia: the case of the city of Križevci ESG for Social Housing Marmalade Lane	Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15)
Spatial Agency	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Sustainability Urban Commons Social Value	85 Social Housing Units in Cornellà DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Die Baupiloten Berlin La Borda Navarinou Park Participatory Planning: Re-examining Community Consultation as a process that integrates the Urban Room method with a digital mapping tool	Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9)
Sustainability Built Environment	Design, planning and building	Social Sustainability Transdisciplinarity	Deben Fields (Garrison Lane) ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation Knight's Walk (Lambeth's Homes) North Wingfield Road social housing complex. Patch22	Karim Hadjri (supervisor) Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Sustainability (5)	Community participation			Joris Hoesktra (Co-supervisor) Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Sustainability (11)	Design, planning and building			Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESR 5)
Sustainability (13)	Community participation			Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)
Sustainability (18)	Design, planning and building			Saskia Furman (ESR 2)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
Sustainability (32)	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Social Sustainability Energy retrofit Indoor Thermal Comfort Life Cycle Costing Housing Affordability Measuring Housing Affordability Building Decarbonisation Spatial Agency Framework Environmentally Sustainable Social Housing Housing Quality	DARE to Build, Chalmers University of Technology Deben Fields (Garrison Lane) ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation HOUSEFUL: Els Mestres, Sabadell Marmalade Lane Rural Studio York's Duncombe Square Housing: Towards Affordability, Sustainability, and Healthier Living	Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9)
Targeted Universalism	Policy and financing	Just Transition		Tijn Croon (ESR 11)
Techno-optimism	Design, planning and building		HOUSEFUL: Els Mestres, Sabadell	Saskia Furman (ESR 2)
Thermal Insulation and Airtightness	Design, planning and building	Affordability Housing Retrofit Energy Retrofit Indoor Thermal Comfort Window Guidance Performance Gap		Saskia Furman (ESR 2)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
		in Retrofit Building Decarbonisation		
Third place	Design, planning and building	Social Sustainability Urban Commons Placemaking Social Value		Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR 15)
Transdisciplinarity (35)	Design, planning and building	Co-creation Critical Utopian Action Research BIM Sustainability Built Environment Mass Customisation Life Cycle Costing		Annette Davis (ESR 1)
Transdisciplinarity (9)	Policy and financing			Marko Horvat (ESR 6)
Transdisciplinarity (7)	Community participation			Androniki Pappa (ESR 13) Alexandra Paio (supervisor)
Trauma Informed Design	Design, planning and building		Hope Street	Anna Martin (ESR 7)
Urban Commons	Community participation	Co-creation Participatory Approaches Community Empowerment Social Sustainability	Lleialtat Santsenca Civic Centre Mehr als wohnen – More than housing Navarinou Park	Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)
Urban Informality	Design, planning and building			Andreas Panagidis (ESR 8)

Concept	Area	Related terms	Related case studies	Authors
				Effrosyni Roussou (ESR 9) Zoe Tzika (ESR 10) Androniki Pappa (ESR 13)
Viability	Design, planning and building	Affordability	Housing Retrofit Subsidies in the Netherlands	Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)
Window Guidance	Policy and financing	Housing Retrofit Housing Regime Just Transition Asset-based Welfare		Marietta Haffner (supervisor) Alex Fernandez (ESR 12)

Annex 2 - Guidelines

This Annex contains the guidelines provided to users.

RE-DWELL Vocabulary

The RE-DWELL Vocabulary is part of the collaborative construction of a knowledge repository on affordable and sustainable housing. The vocabulary consists of definitions of key terms related to the combined research conducted by the 15 early-stage researchers. Each term has multiple definitions, each connected to one of the three main research areas: Design, Construction and Planning; Community Involvement; and Policy and Funding.

The joint construction of this vocabulary allows the researchers' projects to be interwoven. As such, the vocabulary is a tool for conducting transdisciplinary research on affordable and sustainable housing.

Entries are reviewed by RE-DWELL researchers and supervisors. The vocabulary is regularly updated.

Vocabulary construction

The proposal to write an entry comes from the early-stage researcher, and their supervisors. The term can be related to the ESRs' research project, a paper jointly written by researchers, a secondment, etc. ; writing an entry is an opportunity for a deeper study of the concept, to delimit their meanings, and to share them with other researchers.

The description of a term must take into account the theme of the network research: affordable and sustainable housing. Each entry can be related to only one of the three research areas. If there are many involved, the most relevant one should be selected.

The recommended number of characters for each entry (not including references) is 600-800 words.

The name of the term must be kept simple, a single term (e.g. "BIM") or a compound of two or three terms (e.g. "Housing retrofit").

The entry can be written by one single researcher or by several researchers.

Figures might be included; they need to be referenced in the text.

A reference list must be included. APA is used as referencing style.

References are entered in the RE-DWELL group in Mendeley. In the VOCABULARY folder, a new folder is created with the name of the term and the references are inserted there.

Editorial process

The entry is peer-reviewed, first by the supervisor and if necessary by a second RE-DWELL supervisor/co-supervisor.

The peer-reviewed entry is sent to the coordinator for final editorial reviewing. The .doc file is uploaded to Teams RE-DWELL ESRs/VOCABULARY/TERMS/[NAME OF TERM]/REVIEW

Once the reviewing is completed, the final entry is uploaded to the website by the coordinator.